

Teaching Readiness of Junior High School Teachers on the Implementation of Inclusive Education

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Abstract. This study aimed to assess the teaching readiness of secondary school teachers in the context of implementing inclusive education. Inclusive education, which involves educating students with diverse abilities and needs within mainstream classrooms, has become a crucial aspect of contemporary educational systems. Moreover, the study's respondents comprised 120 selected junior high school teachers in the public school district Mati South, Division of the City of Mati. The findings revealed extensive teaching readiness in terms of integrative qualities, cognitive readiness, psychological readiness, and professional readiness. The extent of inclusive education implementation in terms of the initial, transition, and inclusion phases was extensive. There was a significant relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. Moreover, all domains of teaching readiness influence the inclusive education indicators. This study's findings emphasize the intricate relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. By recognizing and addressing teaching readiness challenges, educators can create an inclusive learning environment that fosters the success and well-being of all students, regardless of their unique learning needs. The findings from this study provide valuable insights into the current state of teaching readiness among secondary teachers. These insights can inform educational institutions and policymakers in developing targeted professional development programs, support systems, and policy changes to enhance teachers' preparedness for inclusive education.

KEY WORDS

1. teaching readiness teachers
2. implementation of inclusive education
3. unique learning needs

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1. Introduction

The current stage of the education system's development is characterized by the introduction of inclusive education for children with disabilities in general educational organizations. Inclusive Education” suggests investigating the preparedness of a specific group of teachers in junior high schools to implement inclusive education practices in their classrooms. Inclusive

education is an approach that seeks to provide all students, regardless of their abilities or disabilities, with equal opportunities to learn and participate in school activities. A student with disabilities is an individual who has limitations in physical and (or) psychological development, confirmed by the psychological, medical, and pedagogical commission and these disabilities

hinder education without creating special conditions. One of the main conditions for inclusion is that specially trained teachers should work in general education organizations, who are able to organize psychological and pedagogical support for the development of children with different nosologically groups (AMURCON 2020) mandates an accountability system for all students, including those with special needs. It is evident that schools are under increasing pressure to involve them in many aspects of general education curriculum, assessment, and instruction. In response to legislative and policy changes, a growing number of schools and districts across the United States are adopting models that integrate students with disabilities into the general education environment (Thousand, Villa and Nevin, 2019). In the global context, teachers play a role in helping children succeed. It is the teacher, not a program or the curriculum that has the greatest impact on the education of children with special needs. Research has shown that weak students who are taught by teachers with good instructional practices will outscore and excel, rather than average students whose teachers did not use appropriate instruction. The increased enrolment of children with special needs in special education (SPED) centers, special classes, and regular classes creates a significant challenge for the realization of the preparation program (Abudu, 2019). In the national context, According to Haeefele (2018), special education indicates specially created instruction that meets the unique education and related requirements of an exceptional child. It is distinguished from typical educational programs for non-exceptional children by some unusual quality, something uncommon and noteworthy. It is something special – special materials, special training tactics, unique equipment, and unique aids and special facilities may be required for special categories of children having special needs. Most of these children live in rural and far-flung areas whose parents need to be aware of the educational op-

portunities that these children have, the second option is inclusion or placement of the child with disabilities in general education or regular class where he/she learns with his/her peers under a teacher. Archer and/or SPED-trained teacher who addresses the child's needs. The increased enrolment of children with special needs in special education (SPED) centers, special classes, and regular classes creates a significant challenge for the realization of the preparation program (Abudu, 2019). The study's importance is due to the organization and application of inclusive education, one of the main focuses of the state's educational strategy. Teachers' professional and personal readiness to perform professional activities under inclusive education conditions is a unique demand for new approaches to the education of children with disabilities that are focused on addressing their needs. According to many researchers, one of the important conditions for the implementation of inclusive education is the training of competent teachers who are able and ready to work with children with disabilities (Karynbaeva et al., 2019). Visually impaired youngsters might require reading materials in significant print or Braille. Hearing-impaired kids may well require hearing aid, auditory training, lip reading, etc. Orthopedically handicapped children may need wheelchairs, and the removal of architectural barriers. Accordingly, to Odom et al., (2020), making sense of research and applying it in one's instructional decision-making requires some knowledge, skills, and attitudes. In this series of articles, we hope to provide readers of LDRP with tools to help make sense of critical aspects of research studies and reviews of research so that they can understand and apply research findings to inform and improve policy and practice for learners with disabilities. In this regard, this article is aimed at studying the cognitive component of teachers' readiness for inclusive education of children with disabilities. The leading method for study-

ing this problem is an experimental study and identification of the formation level of the cognitive component of readiness among teachers of educational organizations for inclusive education (Olga, Shapovalova, Shklyar, Emelyanova, Borisova, 2020). During the experimental work, a questionnaire was carried out; questions were presented regarding the necessary knowledge, skills, and work skills, characterizing the cognitive component of teachers' readiness for inclusive education. Therefore, the present study, aimed at studying the level of formation of the cognitive component of teachers' readiness for inclusive education, seems relevant, timely, and appropriate. The novelty of the work is presented by an original diagnostic technique and a significant amount of evidence characterizing the cognitive component of teachers' readiness for inclusive education. The experimental base of the research was formed by educational institutions of Birobidzhan City and the Jewish Autonomous Region. 150 teachers took part in the experiment (Ryndak, 2020). Given that

inclusive education is one of the main focuses of the state's educational strategy, the study's importance stems from how it is organized and carried out. Teachers' professional and personal readiness to perform professional activities in inclusive education is a unique requirement made by new approaches to the education of children with disabilities, which are focused on meeting their needs (Pijl, 2018). This study aimed to highlight the readiness of selected secondary teachers to implement inclusive education. The purpose of the study is to highlight the readiness and how inclusive education will be implemented. Readiness is a system considered to have integrative qualities, cognitive readiness, psychological readiness, and professional readiness that ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical activity in the context of inclusive education of children with disabilities in educational institutions. One of the factors that contributed to its success was teachers' cognitive readiness to organize an innovative educational process.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the research design, research locale, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, ethical considerations and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—The research design of this study, a non-experimental descriptive-correlational method, was chosen for its relevance to the study's focus on the readiness of selected junior high school teachers and the implementation of inclusive education. This design, as described by Creswell (2015), describes and measures the degree of relationship between two variables, in this case, the readiness of teachers and the implementation of inclusive education. The significance and role of each variable under study are fully understood and presented, as outlined by Cohen et al. (2000) and Morrison (1994). The researcher believes that a descriptive correlational study

is effective for this study because of the two variables that are present, the independent variable readiness in selected junior high school teachers and the dependent variable implementation of inclusive education, that the researcher may meet their perspective on both variables. In this research design, the researcher may be able to determine the relationship between the two variables, and it was the most accurate design that could be used in accordance with the topic. This study was conducted within the public junior high school in the division of District Mati South, Division of City of Mati. The chosen school was committed to fulfilling a variety of holistic missions, such as providing an excellent

educational experience and engaging in research activities in collaboration with local, regional, national, and international partners in the implementation of inclusive education; the said study was suitable in pursuing the best venture.

2.2. *Research Respondents*—The study's respondents were 120 selected junior high school teachers in the public school district Mati South, Division of the City of Mati. The researcher chose the inclusion criteria; all 120 respondents must be teachers at a junior high school public school in District Mati South, Division of the City of Mati. The research respondents honestly filled up the information needed in the structured survey questionnaire that was distributed accordingly. The researcher used a simple random sampling method in conducting the study. The researcher used random sampling a subset of individuals chosen from a large set. Everyone was chosen randomly and entirely by chance, such that everyone has the probability of being chosen at any stage during the sampling process. The researcher took the survey seriously to gather results to match and be accepted by the statistician.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—A researcher's self-made instrument was prepared with the guidance of the thesis adviser and evaluators and was used in gathering the needed data for the realization of the work. The questionnaire has 4 aspects (indicators) for the independent variable (readiness in selected secondary teach-

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The necessary data underwent the following gathering procedure: The researcher asked for an endorsement to conduct the study from the Dean of the Graduate School. A letter request attached with the Dean's endorsement was forwarded to the School's Division Superintendent for permission. The researcher asks permission from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of the City of Mati to conduct a

ers) integrative qualities, cognitive readiness, psychological readiness, and professional readiness, while for the dependent variable (implementation of inclusive education) considered the 4 indicators such as meeting learners needs, special requirements, professional functions, and professional activities. Each indicator has five (5) questions that can be answered through the given legend. Simple instructions could be seen in the questionnaires. The research questionnaires where purely researcher made the concept of the questionnaire was submitted and was evaluated by a grammarian and validators. The suggestions and evaluation tools were given for them to help the researcher to improve and make the research instrument in its best form. The outcome of the evaluation and validation, as well as the research instrument's draft, was submitted to the research adviser for finalization. Unclear statements were removed; weak statements were strengthened and polished. After the finalization by the research adviser, the research instrument is now prepared. After the evaluation and approval of the questionnaires, a face-to-face modality was used as a process for gathering data. The researcher administered the questionnaires. The pilot testing was conducted in the same area but not with the study respondents. The first part measures the extent of junior high school teachers' teaching readiness.

survey of the 120 junior high school teachers' respondents from District Mati South, Division of the City of Mati. The researcher scheduled the date to be followed in administering and gathering data as May 2023, considering the leisure time of the teacher respondents so that the researcher could not distract classes. Likewise, the granted letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent was brought to the principals and supervisor of public sec-

Range of Scale and Descriptive Interpretation

Range of Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4:20-5:00	Very Extensive	Teaching readiness of a secondary teacher is always evident.
3:40-4.19	Extensive	Teaching readiness of a secondary teacher is often-times evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Teaching readiness of a secondary teacher is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Teaching readiness of a secondary teacher is rarely evident.
1:00-1.79	Not Extensive	Teaching readiness of a secondary teacher is never evident.

Range of Scale and Descriptive Interpretation

Range of Scale	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4:20-5:00	Very Extensive	Implementation of inclusive education is always evident.
3:40-4.19	Extensive	Implementation of inclusive education is often-times evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	Implementation of inclusive education is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Implementation of inclusive education is rarely evident.
1:00-1.79	Not Extensive	Implementation of inclusive education is never evident.

ondary schools, District Mati South, Division of the City of Mati for the arrangement of the conduct of the research study. The arrangement was made with the school principals and supervisor upon observation of safety protocol regarding the conduct of the research. Uthe approval, the researcher personally administered the research survey tool. The researcher conducted the survey and retrieved the data. The researcher observed full ethical standards in the conduct of the study, following the study protocol assessment and standardized criteria, particularly in

managing the population and data. A received copy of the letter presented was secured from the principals to vouch that the researcher honestly conducted and collected the data from the respondents of the study. The data gathered was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially and accordingly. The results of this study were analyzed and interpreted based on its purpose. The responses may be retrieved and tallied and then forwarded to the statistician for data treatment. The 120 junior high school teachers' respondents from District Mati

South, Division of the City of Mati, have given their free will to participate or to withdraw from the study without any form of consequence or penalty. The respondents personally and professionally gave information that may be required in the study, which was kept private and was treated with utmost confidentiality of the respondents' data was adhered upon. On the other

hand, the research questionnaire used is free of technical terms and could be easily understood by the respondents of the study, these perceived biases are prevented. Therefore, no research questionnaire was given to respondents without permission from the authorized command channels.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—Statistical Tools. The data collected was analyzed using the following statistical tools: Mean Score was used to establish the extent of teaching readiness of junior

high school teachers. Pearson r was used to determine the relationship between the teaching readiness of junior high school teachers and the extent to which inclusive education was implemented.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents a discussion of the findings of this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted.

Summary of the extent of teaching readiness Presented in Table 1 are data on the summary of the extent of teaching readiness. The overall mean of the data is 4.00, which is distributed by the indicators. They were presented with the corresponding mean as follows: inte-

grative qualities 3.96, cognitive readiness 4.00, psychological readiness 4.01, and professional readiness 4.01. All these indicators have the descriptive equivalent of extensive, which means that they may be considered in this study in reading difficulties.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of Teaching Readiness

No.	Indicators	Mean (\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Integrative Qualities	3.96	Extensive
2	Cognitive Readiness	4.00	Extensive
3	Psychological Readiness	4.01	Extensive
4	Professional Readiness	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.00	Extensive

This implied that Summary of the extent of teaching readiness. Teachers' readiness to work in conditions of inclusive education is considered through two main indicators: professional readiness and psychological readiness. Professional preparedness is based on information

readiness, possession of pedagogical technologies, knowledge of the basics of psychology and correctional pedagogy, knowledge of individual differences in children, readiness of teachers to simulate a lesson and use variability in the learning process. The critical level shows that

teachers have an insufficient level of proficiency in professional knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary to organize the educational process, considering the individual and age characteristics of the development of children with disabilities; they are not ready to provide psychological and pedagogical support for children using modern special technologies and methods (Karynbaeva, 2019). Teachers need advice and guidance. Thus, the study showed that most teachers of general education organizations are not sufficiently oriented in the principles of correctional education, in the requirements for the content of education of schoolchildren with different nosological groups, in special methods of teaching subjects, in the knowledge of etiopathogenetic factors affecting the development of a child, in the basics of psychodiagnostics and in the knowledge of study methods. Teachers possess fragmentary professional knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for the organization of the educational process in inclusive education, considering the individual and age-specific devel-

opment of children with disabilities. They are not fully aware of the specifics of the organization of correctional teaching and educational work. They showed only a partial formation of ideas about inclusive education of children with disabilities. The revealed features of the formation of the cognitive component of readiness for inclusive education indicate the need to work with teachers to improve their professional competence (Karynbaeva, Shapovalova, Shklyar, Emelyanova, Borisova, 2019).

Summary of Implementation of Inclusive Education

The table below shows the Summary of Implementation of inclusive education. It plays a crucial role in their reading abilities. Reading difficulties can be influenced by various cognitive factors, including working memory, phonological awareness, visual attention, and background knowledge. These cognitive processes impact students' reading fluency, comprehension, and overall academic achievement.

Table 2. Summary of Implementation of Inclusive Education

Indicators	Mean (\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
Initial Phase	4.02	Extensive
Transition Phase	3.99	Extensive
Inclusion Phase	4.05	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.01	Extensive

Table 2 presented a summary of the implementation of inclusive education, which revealed an overall mean of 4.01. The three indicators are presented with their corresponding mean rating namely Initial Phase 4.02, Transition Phase 3.99, and Inclusion Phase 4.05. All three indicators are with the descriptive equivalent of extensive. This means that an overall mean of 4.01 with the descriptive equivalent of extensive means that the implementation of inclusive education in terms of the inclusion phase

is oftentimes evident. Implementation of inclusive education in terms of the inclusion phase is oftentimes evident, and the implementation of inclusive education in terms of the inclusion phase is oftentimes evident. This implied that implementation of inclusive education in terms of the inclusion phase this study stems from the fact that very little is known about the practice of educational inclusion in the Philippines. The absence of a shared approach to education in the country, one that is open to all students, sug-

gests that a strong conceptual basis for inclusive education remains to be established. A significant relationship between the teaching readiness and implementation of inclusive education

The significant relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education has a strong relationship in work. It is necessary to be united and to have work collaboration, which can be gained by having both positive teaching readiness and implementation of inclusive education. It is the teacher,

not a program or the curriculum, that has the greatest impact on the education of children with special needs. It is evident that schools are under increasing pressure to involve them in many aspects of general education curriculum, assessment, and instruction. In response to legislative and policy changes, many schools and districts across the United States are adopting models that integrate students with disabilities into the general education environment (Thousand, Villa and Nevin, 2019).

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between the Teaching Readiness and Implementation of Inclusive Education

Variables	Mean	Std	R	Sig. Level	Decision
Teaching Readiness	4.00	.400	.412	.000	Reject Ho
Implementation of Inclusive Education	4.01	.401			

Table 3 shows a significant relationship between teaching readiness and inclusive education implementation. Teaching readiness got a mean rating of 4.00 with a standard deviation of 0.400, and inclusive education implementation got a mean rating of 4.01 with a standard deviation of 0.401. The Pearson-R correlation result showed 0.412, which means there is a positive correlation at a significant level of .000. This means that there is a significant relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. It explains that teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education significantly influence each variable. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis of the study stated that there is no significant relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education; the result of the study implied that the indicators of teaching readiness significantly influence the implementation of inclusive education of learners. Hence, the deci-

sion is to reject the null hypothesis. However, as evidenced by the literature review, many studies have been done on the implementation of inclusive education, which can be influenced by various factors; teachers have been acknowledged as key stakeholders in curriculum change. Thus, supporting teachers in making the change possible is crucial to the achievement of curriculum goals and objectives of the implementation of inclusive education. This study will unveil the nature and extent of support rendered for curriculum implementation of inclusive education, and this may help provide an avenue for improvement. The domain of teaching readiness significantly influence the implementation of inclusive education

The domain of teaching readiness of secondary teachers in terms of integrative qualities, cognitive readiness, psychological readiness, and professional readiness significantly influences the implementation of inclusive education in terms of the initial phase, transition phase,

and inclusion phase. obtained will provide the initial self-evaluation for teachers to measure their competence in dealing with children with special needs and to the teaching requirements for learners to achieve an effective learning process. To provide teachers with baseline information in developing future educational programs, teaching strategies, and techniques. An application of inclusive education, one of the main focuses is a system of integrative qualities, prop-

erties, knowledge, and personal skills that ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical activity in the context of inclusive education of children with disabilities in educational institutions. of the state’s educational strategy, accounts for the study’s importance, considering the factors of the professional and personal readiness of teachers to perform professional activities in the implementation of inclusive education.

Table 4. The Domain of Teaching Readiness Significantly Influences the Implementation of Inclusive Education

Independent Variables (Domains)	Dependent Variable	F	p-value	Decision on Ho1
Integrative Qualities	Implementation of Inclusive Education	4.106	0.001	Reject Ho
Cognitive Readiness	Implementation of Inclusive Education	4.112	0.005	Reject Ho
Psychological Readiness	Implementation of Inclusive Education	5.106	0.001	Reject Ho
Professional Readiness	Implementation of Inclusive Education	5.106	0.001	Reject Ho

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F
Sig.	Decision			
1 Regression	5.660	2	2.830	26.43
.000	Reject Ho			
Residual	6.960	65		
Total	12.619	67		

a. Teaching Readiness
b. Implementation of Inclusive Education

Table 4 shows that the domain of teaching readiness significantly Influences the implementation of inclusive education. The value of the regression analysis F ratio is 26.43, with a significant level of .000. This implies that the teach-

ing readiness indicators significantly influence the implementation of inclusive education. The decision is to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that a domain of teaching readiness indicators significantly influences the implemen-

tation of inclusive education. It plays a crucial role in teaching readiness indicators, as teachers need to process and integrate information from the text. According to Haefele (2018), special education indicates specially created instruction that meets an exceptional child's unique education and related requirements. It is distinguished from typical educational programs for non-exceptional children by some unusual quality, something uncommon, and noteworthy. It is something special special materials, training tactics, unique equipment, and unique aids and special facilities may be required for special categories of children with special needs. However, there are different terms used to refer to

how ready selected secondary teachers are to implement inclusive education implementation to become more involved in sports; aside from academic involvement, we need to consider the importance of inclusive education and the preparation or readiness of teachers in teaching special students. This study also differs from its locality because most of them are from other localities and countries. Furthermore, this study is relative to society's current situation because the readiness of selected secondary teachers to implement inclusive education is more demanding and beneficial, providing students with opportunities to practice and further develop what they have learned in school.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter discusses the research's focal points and the results of the statistical analysis. It also presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the study's findings.

4.1. Findings—This study aimed to determine the relationship between teaching readiness indicators significantly influence the implementation of inclusive education. The extent of teaching readiness in terms of integrative qualities (3.96), cognitive readiness(4.00), psychological readiness(4.01), and professional readiness (4.01) was extensive. The extent of implementations of inclusive education in terms of the initial phase (4.02), transitions phase (3.99), and inclusions phase (4.05) was extensive. Moreover, the Pearson-R correlation result means there was a positive correlation at a significant level of teaching readiness, which means that there was a significant relationship between the teaching readiness indicators significantly influencing the implementation of inclusive education. It explains that if the teaching readiness were positively embodied the implementation of inclusive education of learners is vertically significant and very extensive. The decision was to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there was a significant relationship between teaching

readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. The results of the study disclosed that the teaching readiness implementation of inclusive education significantly influences the implementation of inclusive education of learners. Reading difficulties could impact various cognitive processes, shaping how learners perceive, process, and comprehend written information. The domain of teaching readiness holds a significant influence on the implementation of inclusive education of learners, teaching readiness, such as poor phonological awareness, limited working memory capacity, or challenges in visual attention, could hinder students' ability to effectively engage with and understand the text. The findings based on the statement "The domain of teaching readiness holds a significant influence on the implementation of inclusive education of learners" and the mention of teaching readiness challenges such as poor phonological awareness, limited working memory capacity, and challenges in visual attention could be summarized as follows. The study's null hypothesis

stated that there was no significant relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. The study's result implied that the indicators of teaching readiness significantly influence the implementation of inclusive education. Hence, the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. However, the study's results disclosed that teaching readiness significantly influences the implementation of inclusive education. The ability to read and comprehend written text was a fundamental skill that supported numerous cognitive processes and intellectual growth. This study would give an idea to the higher positions to understand the situation of the special students and consider other readiness of selected secondary teachers on the implementation of inclusive education towards some factors was a kind of extracurricular involvement conveys to teachers that outcome and performance-oriented are interested and invested in students' development considering the training and how ready might be done for the implementation of inclusive education in the secondary school. For this reason, teaching readiness plays a pivotal role in the successful implementation of inclusive education for diverse learners. This study has highlighted the impact of teaching readiness challenges, including poor phonological awareness, limited working memory capacity, and difficulties in visual attention, on students' ability to effectively engage with and comprehend educational content. In conclusion, the findings of this study emphasize the intricate relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. By recognizing and addressing teaching readiness challenges, educators could create an inclusive learning environment that fosters the success and well-being of all students, regardless of their unique learning needs. This study is timely and needs to be addressed immediately to provide proper actions and recommendations to all school stakeholders. Thus, there were many challenges concerning the readiness of

secondary teachers for the implementation of inclusive education.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the overall findings of this research, the following conclusions were drawn: The extent of teaching readiness in terms of integrative qualities, cognitive readiness, psychological readiness, and professional readiness was extensive. The extent of inclusive education implementation in terms of the initial phase, transitions phase, and inclusions phase was extensive. There was a significant relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. All domains of teaching readiness influence the inclusive education indicators. This study's findings emphasize the intricate relationship between teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. By recognizing and addressing teaching readiness challenges, educators could create an inclusive learning environment that fosters the success and well-being of all students, regardless of their unique learning needs.

4.3. Recommendations—Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were offered for consideration: Given the study's results indicating a significant relationship between teaching readiness and the successful implementation of inclusive education, it was advisable for educational institutions and policymakers to prioritize and invest in enhancing teaching readiness among educators. This could include providing training, resources, and support to educators to better prepare them for inclusive education settings. Additionally, ongoing research in this area may further uncover specific indicators of teaching readiness that have the most significant impact on the implementation of inclusive education, allowing for more targeted interventions and improvements in inclusive educational practices. The officials of the Department of Education may consider making initiatives to develop further, in conclusion, the domain of

teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education. By addressing these difficulties and promoting effective teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education, we can positively impact students' cognitive growth, academic achievement, and lifelong learning abilities. The School Heads may observe their responsibility as school leaders to address and support students with reading difficulties. Implementing evidence-based practices and providing targeted interventions that would help students overcome these challenges and enhance their cognitive development. By addressing teaching readiness and the implementation of inclusive education growth but also fostering a positive learning environment. When students gain confidence in their reading abilities, it opens doors to a vast array of knowledge, experiences, and opportunities. School heads may be allocated resources, provided with professional development opportunities, and encouraged to create a school culture that prioritizes effective reading instruction and intervention. The Learners may consider the results an important factor for self-development. The domain of reading difficulties significantly influences cognitive development in students. Addressing these difficulties and promoting effective reading instruction can positively impact students' cognitive growth, academic achievement, and lifelong learning abilities. The results and findings of this study would challenge future researchers to conduct a similar study that must consider other factors that could help the new education system in the Philippines quality and valuable in all aspects. Lastly, by implementing these recommendations, educational institutions and policymakers may work toward fostering a more inclusive educational environment that benefits all students, regardless of their diverse needs and backgrounds.

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